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Discernment and Discipleship

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Pope Francis, addressing the Polish Jesuits in Crakow, said: “Today the Church needs to grow in discernment, in the ability to discern. And priests, above all, really need it for their ministry. This is why we need to teach it to seminarians and priests in formation: they are the ones usually entrusted with the confidences of the conscience of the faithful. Spiritual direction is not solely a priestly charism, but also lay, it is true. But, I repeat, you must teach this above all to priests, helping them in the light of the Exercises in the dynamic of pastoral discernment, which respects the law but knows how to go beyond. .. We need to truly understand this: in life not all is black on white or white on black. No! The shades of grey prevail in life. We must teach them to discern in this grey area.” Following this invitation of our Pope Francis, we shall consider here the spiritual journey of Peter the Apostle in his following of Jesus of Nazareth: the process of discerning spirit.

Discernment comes from the Spanish word “discernir” or Latin “discernere” meaning : to know, judge, comprehend, discern, separate, distinguish, or discriminate. The word discernment in the Spiritual Exercises indicates an action involving activities not only of the mind but also of the heart. To discern the Spirit I must live within my life. I must be really present to myself here and now. And at the still-point of my

self-hood, in the ambience of my God-awareness, my God-desire, I choose and respond, continuing to notice the congruence of my choice with my God-desire, and my growing freedom to live as I live out the consequences. Discernment requires bringing my present life situation to where God touches me.

Following Ignatius's guidelines we can find three steps of the learning process: (1) *How we trace the consolation and desolation in our feelings and how we get in touch with them,* (2) *How we understand these feelings and the thoughts of projects linked with them, and* (3) *How we perceive what they mean and where they tend, that is, their dynamic relationship to the end.* Pierre Jacobs called the three steps as a holistic approach of discernment : (1) FEEL, (2) WHAT DOES IT MEAN AND WHERE DOES IT LEAD? and (3) TAKE A STANCE : FOLLOW IT OR REJECT IT.

The discipleship of Peter: Lk 5,1 ff describes the event of Jesus calling Peter at the Lake of Gennaesaret (Galilee). Peter, astonished at the catch of fish, falls down, saying :”Leave me, Lord, for I am a sinful man.”. And Jesus, knowing very well what goes on in Peter's heart, tells him “Do not be afraid. You will catch people from now on.”. This journey of Peter following Jesus continues till the end of his life. Here we shall accompany Peter as he grows from being a disciple to becoming an apostle. The initiative is always from the Lord Jesus (Lk 6,12-13 and Mk 3,13). Jesus, after spending the whole night in prayer on the mountain, comes down to the plains and calls his disciples one by one, naming them and appoints them apostles.: “he calls those whom he wanted to be with him [disciples] and to be sent out on mission” [apostles]. This choice of the Twelve is at the beginning of his public ministry and this is the starting of the formation of these Twelve in becoming disciples. The living out of this discipleship was not just for one moment but it is a life-long journey, a pilgrimage of discipleship, a process of becoming disciples.

In the Indian tradition a disciple [*sishya*] sits at the feet of a *guru* and learns. And the *sishya* learns from the *guru* the art of leading oneself “from the false self to the true self, from darkness to light and from death to immortality”. In Mk 8, 27-33 Mark narrates how Peter is unaware of the presence of the two kinds of forces/movements/thoughts: one coming from the Father and the other from Satan and how Jesus opens the eyes of Peter to the reality of such movements. And Jesus would have shared his own personal experience with his disciples, and in particular with Peter as he has to “confirm others in faith later”, by narrating to them his own experience of the “Temptations in the Desert” : Lk 4, 1- 13.

It is very inspiring to us who want to be the disciples of Jesus to be aware of the slow and steady growth of Peter in the spirit of discernment. In Jn 13, 2-15 when Jesus comes to Peter we see how he reacts first and how Jesus opens his “blind eyes” (Jn 13, 6-10). In the narrative of Jesus’ agony at the Garden of Gethsemane, Jesus is struggling against the temptation to give up his mission offered to him by his Abba and Peter is sleeping:”Simon, are you sleeping?...The spirit indeed is eager but human nature is weak.”(Mk 14,37-38).

The impulsive character of Peter again is revealed at the moment when Jesus was arrested at the Garden of Olives: Jn 18,10-11: “Put your sword into its sheath; Should I not drink the cup which the Father has given me?”. The denial of Peter and his repentance at the compassionate glance of Jesus is a very good example of Peter’s ‘blindness’ because of his love for his Master on the one hand and his fear of losing his life on the other. And the merciful glance of Jesus brought out tears of repentance in Peter (Lk 22, 54-62). And after the resurrection of Jesus, the Risen Lord appearing to the Seven at the Lake of Tiberias and after the breakfast prepared and offered by Jesus to them, he invites Peter to that great grace of discernment: Jn 21, 15-19: “ Simon, son of John, do you love me more than these?” and Peter’s humble reply:”Yes, Lord, you know that I love you.”. Here Jesus the Risen Lord foretells the cost Peter

will have to pay for following Jesus as his close disciple. And after the coming of the Holy Spirit, one could notice the marvelous change in Peter: his awareness of himself and his boldness to proclaim that the Jesus of Nazareth the Risen Lord to the large crowd (AA 2,14ff) and before the Council of Jewish leaders (AA 4,8-14).

Only after the coming of the Holy Spirit will these first disciples of Jesus be able to realize the grace of discernment. So much so that Peter in his First letter chapter 5, 8-9 will warn: “Be sober and alert because your enemy the devil prowls about like a roaring lion seeking someone to devour”. “Stand your ground firm in your faith, knowing that our brothers and sisters, scattered throughout the world, are confronting similar persecutions”. In persecution too Peter sees the work of the devil, who does his best to discourage those who hope in Christ. It is a proven fact that when we get ready to make some commitment in the service of Christ, many unexpected obstacles arise.

Besides, there is the need for the grace of “discovering what is more pleasing to the Lord, given the option for two equally seemed good inspirations”. Take for example Lk 10, 38-42, where Jesus is at the house of Martha and Mary. When Martha complains to Jesus about her sister Mary, Jesus tells her that Mary has chosen the better part. In other words, at this moment what Jesus would need was just the presence of Martha and Mary - not the food. On other occasions Jesus would have needed food but at this moment what he needs is just rest. Martha was invited to seek that which would be more pleasing to her Master and Friend. Discernment enables a person to find out that which is “more conducive to fulfill what God desires”, i.e. the goal of one’s existence and consequently to grow in one’s spirit of discipleship [SE 21].

Basing himself on such experiences of Peter, Ignatius, in his Spiritual Exercises, invites the exercitant/retreatant to dispose himself/herself for the grace of “not being deaf to the call of

Christ the King but ready and diligent to accomplish his most holy will” in the King Exercise/ Kingdom Meditation [SE 91-98]. This is the starting point of becoming a disciple of Christ: to be with Him (*mecum*). The exercitant is taken up with the call of Christ the King and wants to follow Him at all costs. Like Peter the exercitant is invited to become aware of the implication of becoming a disciple of Christ. His/her generous love is to be discerned properly. It could be a blind love as it was in the case of Ignatius of Loyola at his castle: “the soul was still blind but had a great desire to serve the Lord” [Autobiography 19]. Therefore Ignatius offers the Meditation on Two Standards [SE 136 – 147] so that the eyes of the retreatant be opened; in other words, she/he may become a discerning person: being able to sift the different spirits which are acting in one’s life. In other words, there are in each one of us different movements of thoughts, feelings, images, desires, etc. which take me either towards Christ or away from Christ. Ignatius provides a meditation of Two Standards in which he is asking the retreatant to dispose her/himself for the ‘grace-healed-eyes’: “ to ask for insight into the deceits of the evil leader, and for help to guard myself against them; and further, for insight into the genuine life which the supreme and truthful commander sets forth, and grace to imitate him” [SE 139] . Thus the exercitant comes to greater awareness of the different motivations which enable her/him to follow Christ our Lord.

Triple Areas of the life of a disciple of Christ: First, *discernment in daily life*: every Christian is called to be a discerning person; his/her life-style becomes a way of discernment. Ignatius offers the method of *Consciousness Examen prayer* for one’s deepening of discerning life.

Secondly, *discernment in one’s prayer life* enables her/him to discern the experiences of spiritual consolation / desolation during her / his prayer life. Doing “*Review*”- discerning the movements of the spirits within oneself - at the end of every prayer period helps one to grow in her/his prayer life.

Thirdly, *discernment is made use of for 'decision making'*: to discern what God desires in one's life regarding matters of greater importance. Ignatius, in his spiritual Exercises, provides "Rules for Discernment of Spirits" [SE 313 – 3327 and 328 – 336] and these guidelines provide helps for making the "Election of one's way of living out the discipleship of Christ".

It is the task of the Society to console the faithful and to help with discernment so that the enemy of human nature does not rob us of joy: the joy of evangelizing,

Conclusion: Thus, what our present Pope Francis desires that those who want to be true and authentic disciples of Christ should be enabled to grow in the spirit of discernment: "It is the task of the Society to console the faithful and

to help with discernment so that the enemy of human nature does not rob us of joy: the joy of evangelizing, the joy of the family, the joy of the Church, the joy of creation. That it does not rob from us, neither in discouragement when faced with the greatness of the ills of the world and the misunderstandings between those who presume to do good, nor fill us with fatuous joys that are always to hand in any shop. This 'service of joy and spiritual consolation' is rooted in prayer. It consists of encouraging us and encouraging all to insistently ask for God's consolation."